

Assessment of Guidance and Counselling Services and Their Impact on the Academic Performance of Public Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed role of guidance and counselling services and their impact on the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Two objectives and one hypothesis guided the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted. The study population consisted of all teacher counsellors in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The sample of this study comprised two (2) teacher counsellors, each from one of the fourteen (14) selected schools. The instrument that was used for data collection is a self-constructed questionnaire. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, and ANOVA associated with regression was used to test the hypothesis. The findings revealed that information counselling service and appraisal counselling services significantly affects academic performance of secondary school students Rivers State, Nigeria. The study concluded that counselling practices assist students at various forms at becoming fully acquainted with multiple occupational and educational opportunities that is at their disposal, as well as helps to advance and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students, which will encourage decent behaviour. When various secondary schools employ counselling services that benefits them most with the involvement of educational stakeholders, it will promote the practice of guidance and counselling in schools. It was recommended amongst others that there should be appointment of full-time counsellors in each school, which will address the existing and teething problems of students; guidance and counselling programmes should be totally embedded in the curriculum of secondary schools. This will enable students who are not always willing to see a counsellor to yield for it.

Keywords: Assessment, Guidance and Counseling, Services, Impact, Students, Academic Performance, Public Senior, Secondary School, Rivers State, Nigeria.

Reference to this paper should be made as follows:

Olamuyiwa, F. B. (2025). Assessment of guidance and counselling services and their impact on the academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 18(4), 643-662.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the foundation of meaningful societal development and human capacity building. The process of education is carried out in the school, a place that develops the prospective of an individual and the entrance to academic excellence. Education provides for the creation of awareness, acquisition of requisite skills and knowledge that enable an individual function properly in a society. Educational activities are geared towards ensuring that students achieve mastery of educational objectives. In this period of globalization and industrial revolution, education is seen as a primary step for every human engagement. It plays a vital role in the development of human capital and is linked with an individual's well-being and opportunities for better living (Battle & Lewis, 2012). It guarantees the acquisition of knowledge and skills, which enables individuals to increase their productivity and develop their quality of life. This increase in productivity also leads towards new sources of earning which enhances the economic growth of a country (Saxton, 2000).

The goals of secondary education according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014), is to possibly contribute to national development through series of training; to develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society; to develop the intellectual capacity of individuals to understand and appreciate the local and external environments; to acquire both physical and intellectual skills that will enable individuals to be self-reliant and valuable members of the society; to promote and encourage scholarship and community service; and to promote national and international understanding and interaction. Furthermore, attention was drawn to need for counselling programmes in school.

To safeguard the effective role of education in any society, Egbochuku (2008) pointed out that guidance and counseling services is essential to improve education that will assist in growth and sustenance on any economy. Counselors has significant role to play in the today's Nigeria economic situation where students have lost interest in education that will make them add value to the economy. Guidance counselling is a respected profession whose relevance in the educational system of Nigeria is becoming increasingly recognized by the country's educational planners and policy makers. Ideally a well-trained school counsellor should be available in each institution in the federation to deal with various aspects of students' problems and this presupposes the establishment of school guidance and counselling from the primary up to the tertiary levels (Adeyemo, 2014).

Guidance and counselling is a vital educational tool in influencing the orientation in a child from negative ideas that is planted in the child by his/her peers. Akinade (2012) defined guidance and counselling as a process of aiding an individual realise his/her self and the ways in which he is responding to the influences of his/her environment. Additionally to assists him/her establish some personal meaning for this behaviour and to develop and classify a set of goals and morals for future behaviour. Guidance and counseling is incorporated into the school system to help eradicate overwhelming ignorance of many young people on their choices of career prospects, reduce academic failures and personality maladjustment among school children. Egbo (2013) stated that the total development of a child can only take place in an environment conducive for teaching and learning.

Oniye and Alawane (2008) insisted that guidance and counselling programmes guide students in consolidating their standards, likes, and general abilities to realise their full potential. It leads students on making the right career and course choices, refuting psychological problems, and efficiently adjusting to the school environment. Eyo et al. (2010) stated that guidance is a

programme of services to individuals in line with their needs and the impact of environmental factors. She went ahead to state that guidance and counselling is a professional field which has a broad range of activities, programmes and services geared toward assisting individuals to understand themselves, their problems, their school environment and their world, at the same time to develop adequate capacity for making prudent choices and decisions.

Oluwatimilehin and Owoyele (2012) noted that students who are exposed to educational guidance and counselling services perform in their study better than their counterparts. This explains the need for such practice especially, in public secondary schools and less educationally developing cities, such as Rivers State in Nigeria. Denga (2011) referred to these services as “group of formalised educational services designed by the school to assist students to achieve self-knowledge or self-understanding which is essential for them to attain the fullest self-development and self-realization of their potential”. These services include: student appraisal service, information service, counselling service, placement service, orientation service, referral service, follow-up and evaluation service, and research service. Few studies within the Nigerian region revealed how guidance and counselling services impact students' academic performance without taking cognisance to the “effect”, while considering some of the counselling approaches available in secondary schools. This is the gap the researcher attempt to build on.

Statement of the Problem

Schools success is mostly measured by the level of the students' academic performance. Student's performance is still a major concern for educators. Educational stakeholders have affirmed that the goal of education cannot be achieved without the input of professional counsellors. Students still perform poorly in their academics notwithstanding the various ways in which they are guided either by their teachers or parents. Many school's administrators (principals) in Rivers State are yet to embrace the programme because they are yet to understand the advantages of appropriate counselling services.

Students, most of the times encounter a lot of academic challenges which they find difficult to cope with and, may be attributed to indiscipline, drug addiction, poverty, militancy, non-challant attitude of the students, which eventually results into poor academic performance. There is need to enforce guidance and counselling programmes in schools, to reduce academic failures experienced by secondary school students. Owing to the above challenges identified above in secondary schools, and the lack of clarity on other related studies towards the specific counselling programmes that can possibly affect academic performance of students, this study therefore investigates the effect of information, orientation, placement and appraisal services as forms of guidance and counselling services on academic performance of students.

As such, this study will provide information to various stakeholders such as school counsellors, teachers, school administrators, parents, students, and policy makers on the extent guidance and counselling programme can affect students' academic performance in secondary schools. It will also benefit researchers who might be interested in undertaking future studies on “the effect of guidance and counselling on academic performance of secondary school students” or related topics by serving as a source of data, information and reference to them.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate effect of guidance and counselling on academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State. Specifically, the study is designed to:

- Identify the various types of guidance and counselling services present in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- Ascertain the effect of information counselling services on academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

- What are the various types of guidance and counselling services present in secondary schools in in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- How does information counselling service affect academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were designed for the study:

- Information counselling service does not significantly affect academic performance of secondary school students Rivers State

LITERATURE REVIEW

Education

Education has been seen over time as an important and indispensable key to any form of development (Jibrin & Zayum, 2012). Education in its actual sense comprises all the process individuals go through in life to develop and optionally utilize their potentials through the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes that are necessary for effective living in society (Umar & Cyril, 2012). Generally speaking, it is a process that starts from birth and ends with death which means that education is a lifelong process. Education is an instrument for economic, political and scientific development of all nations (Jibrin et al., 2012). Umar and Haruna (2014) posited that secondary school education is the engine room of knowledge acquisition, a stage at which students come in contact with various subjects, which determine the field of study they will like to pursue in higher secondary school education is kind of level after the primary education and before higher education. Its position in educational system also speaks of its importance. The National policy on Education (FRN, 2014) stated that the aim of education is to inculcate in the child, the spirit of inquiry and secondly, education should equip students to live effectively in our modern age of science and technology. Furthermore, attention was drawn to need for counselling programmes in school.

Guidance and Counselling

Guidance is the aid given to a person who realizes that he/she needs assistance in order to make him/herself a useful and worthwhile citizen of the society which he/she lives in. Egbochuku (2008) asserted that Guidance would enable the individuals to answer such questions as: Who am I? What am I capable of doing? How can I fit into my society? How can I maximally use the opportunities within my environment to achieve my life goals? Counselling on the other hand, is a process of helping individuals or group of people to gain self-understanding in order to be themselves. Counselling is a reflection of a professional relationship between a trained counsellor and a client. The importance of counselling programmes in schools cannot be overemphasized especially with the daily expansion in the enrolment of students in schools, growing needs of youths in Nigeria, the frequent unrest in schools and the recurring changes in the educational system (Bolu-Steve & Oredugba, 2017). Guidance and counselling services have become an indispensable programme in schools and this cannot be done in isolation. Counselling is a learning process in which a counsellor helps an individual or individuals learn, understand themselves and their environment and be in a position to choose the right type of behaviours that will help them develop, grow, progress, ascend, mature and step up, educationally, vocationally and socio personally (Ebizie et al., 2016). In other words, counselling is a transformative process of helping people to learn all that are to be learnt both in and outside the School.

There are two main types of counselling, they are individual counselling (face to face interaction between the professional counsellor and the client) and group counselling (this between the professional counsellor and clients who have similar concern) (Omosho, 2004). The major counselling services/ programmes in schools include: information service, orientation service, placement service, appraisal service, follow-up service, evaluation service, referral service etc. All these services aimed at advancing the academic standard of secondary school students. Counselling services has a lot of impact on students' academic performance. Counsellors play active roles in dealing with the emotional and psychological problems that could mar the academic progress of the students. Denga (2011) noted that students who are exposed to educational guidance and counselling services perform in their study better than their counterparts. Omosho (2004) described that the counselor aids to guide the students in the choice of career that matches with their personality. In the same vein, Egbule (2006) emphasized that educational guidance and counselling services enable students to make appropriate use of their educational opportunities. It aids in planning effective study habit which in turn, enhances students' academic competencies. Furthermore, Adeoye (2016) revealed that counselling services are intervention process that are effective in dealing with student academic problems and at the same time foster healthy heterosexual relationship among the students. The counsellor also keeps proper record of continuous assessment of the academic activities of the students. Through the counsellors effort, the academic deficiencies ranging from slow learning, lack of attention, poor concentration and other learning difficulties are remedied (Yusuf, 2004).

Guidance and Counselling and National Policy on Education (NPE)

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) pointed out that guidance and counseling services are important education services that are essential for successful implementation of the Nigerian educational system. It advocated setting up guidance services as earlier mentioned in all post-primary schools with professionally trained counselors to administer such services. Nigerian

Government in acknowledging the importance of Guidance and Counseling to the country's education system included Guidance in the policy document of the National Policy on Education (1981). Paragraph 83 (II) of the policy document stated clearly that –“in view of the apparent ignorance of many young people about career prospects and in view of personality instability among school children, career officers and counsellors will be appointed in Post-Primary institutions”. Since qualified personnel in this category are scarce, Government will continue to make provisions for the training of interested teachers in guidance and counselling. Guidance and counselling will also feature in teacher education programmes (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1981). The above statement revealed that the planners of the National Policy on Education were aware of the rising need for Guidance services in the Secondary Schools hence its inclusion in the policy document. Also, they were conscious of the problem of young people but were not however well informed about the scope, potentials and objectives of what Guidance and Counselling entails. The 1981 version of the NPE has since undergone a number of revisions with the latest one published in the year 2014. The new National Policy on Education was first introduced by the Federal Government of Nigeria in 1977 and subsequently revised in 1981, 1989, 2004 and 2014, respectively.

Factors that Militate Against Guidance and Counselling in Secondary Schools

Studies have shown that there some factors militate against effective guidance and counselling in public secondary schools. Some of these factors include:

Inadequate funding

Guidance and Counselling teachers need adequate support in undertaking innovative activities towards provision of their services. Several scholars, educators, politicians and even the general public have emphasised the importance of adequate funding and infrastructure. All education administrators should therefore support the teacher's efforts in the process of implementing the guidance and counselling program. Unfortunately most of the head teachers are appointed from amongst serving teachers most of whom lack training in institutional management (Kafwa, 2005). This adversely affects effective management of educational institutions and maintenance of quality and high standards of education including guidance and counseling services. Funding is vital in organizing in-service courses, inspiring and encouraging teachers to expand their time and energy in innovative efforts, explaining and clarifying the objective of innovation to teachers, securing information about teachers' needs and problems, arranging joint meetings with staff and arranging informal meetings for discussions among teachers.

Shortage of Guidance and Counselling Materials

Kochhar (2000) asserted that a teacher who has adequate and relevant teaching materials and facilities will be more confident, effective and productive. Teachers might also have the competence and positive attitudes but when adequate and relevant resources are not provided; their efforts will come to naught. These resources should further be made more accessible to all teachers through establishment of resource centres with staff, audio-visual facilities and equipment and work materials. The provision of facilities and the appropriate use of teaching

resources can provide a conducive environment in which in the long run would facilitate the direct and indirect change of behavior of the students.

Shortage of Trained Teachers

The essence of the guidance and counselling programme comprises of knowledge and attitudes. Training therefore is a central theme. During training, teachers acquire skills and knowledge which they should be able to use in the classroom situation. The process involves the trainees learning to identify and solve problems through arbitration of tutors, therefore feeling qualified. Ololube (2006) pointed out that there is need for efficient short in-service courses which should be conducted on a continuous basis, more so in the wake of any revision of national development objectives and priorities. Fullan (2002) claimed that the quality of education and learning relies heavily on the competence of the teachers; this is because they are in the forefront in the implementation of any school-based programme. The way they have been trained, the extent of their specialisation and the degree of their personal initiative can have curriculum change process.

Effect of Guidance and Counselling Services on Students Academic Performance

Career counsellors offer a wide range of career related programmes to students which are aimed at assisting students to plan their career, make informed decisions and choose a career which will land him or her into the right vocation so as to make students enjoy their work (Eremie & Ibifari, 2018). The strategic position of counsellors in secondary schools enables them in assisting to mould the students' educational, emotional, behavioural and psychological challenges. These counselling services are done in tandem with other school personnel (Orewere, 2012).

Guidance and Counselling is one of the educational services. Educational services as contained in the National Policy of Education (2014) are to "facilitate the implementation of the educational policy, the attainment of policy goals and the promotion of effectiveness of educational system". Again, the third goal of the educational services is to "make learning experiences more meaningful for children". Based on these goals, the guidance and counselling activities in schools are beneficial because what the counsellors working with students in secondary schools guide them thoroughly to help them succeed in their educational pursuit. According to Okobiah and Okorodudu (2006), guidance and counselling is encompassed by activities of relevant services and also processes of helping persons within and outside the school, to achieve their full potentialities in their emotional, moral, social, academic and vocational developments.

Modo et al. (2013) examined guidance and counselling services in secondary school as coping strategy for improved academic performance of students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The population comprised of all SS3 students in public secondary schools in Uyo municipality, Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. A sample size of 252 students responded to the instruments. The data were analysed at 0.05 alpha level using t-test. The result revealed that students who utilised the counselling services performed better than those who did not. It was recommended that all schools should be provided with professional counsellors to help the students.

Eremie and Bethel-Eke (2020) investigated influence of guidance and counselling services on career choice and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers

State. The research adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 66,164 respondents. A sample size of 399 was drawn using the Taro Yamen formula. The study adopted the simple random sampling technique. Means and Standard Deviations were used to answer the research questions, while z-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. It was found that there is no significant difference in the opinion of students on the extent to which educational, vocational and personal social counselling services influence career choice and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State. The study concluded that guidance and counselling services such as educational, vocational and personal social counselling programme in school assist students to harmonise their abilities, interests and values and thereby help them to develop their full potential. The study recommended that schools should be supplied with sufficient manpower in terms of trained counsellors who will be able to guide, direct and assist the students towards achieving their ultimate goal in life.

Eremie and Jackson (2019) examined the Influence of Guidance and Counseling Services on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Rivers State. Four research questions were posed to guide the study and three hypotheses was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance and the researchers used the Survey research design for the study. A sample size of 664 respondents was studied. Test-re-test method was used for the reliability test. The instrument had 16 items which was validated with a reliability coefficient of 0.92 which showed that it was reliable for the study. The mean and standard deviation was used in analysing the research questions, while the z-test was used in testing the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that: Information services significantly influence academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, appraisal and orientation services does not influence students' academic performance. It was therefore recommended that Guidance and counselling programme should be strengthened in order to improve the academic performance of secondary schools in the area.

Tawiah, Alberta, and Bossman (2015) carried out in order to ascertain the impact of guidance and counselling on academic performance. The study area was the Dormaa Senior High School in the Dormaa Central Municipality of the Brong-Ahafo Region of Ghana. Pre-test and post-test control group design was applied for the study. An experimental design was used as the research frame for the study. 40 students were selected; 20 for experimental group and 20 for control group for the study. Two hypotheses were formulated to keep the study in focus. Data from respondents were gathered by the use of interviews. The results of the findings revealed that there is no significant difference of pre-test scores of experimental and control group. However, significant difference was realized between post-test scores of experimental and control group with regards to academic performance. It was recommended that full time counsellors be appointed in each school to address the existing and teething problems of students. It was again recommended that guidance programmes should be seriously included in the curriculum of pre-tertiary institutions.

Atsuwe and Achegbulu (2018) examined influence of guidance and counselling programme on the academic performance of secondary school students in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This study adopted an ex-post facto research design. It targeted all the 5464 population of Form Four students, 21 teacher counsellors and 21 head teachers of the 52 available public secondary schools in the study area. A random sample of 196 students, ten teacher counsellors and ten head teachers were selected from the ten selected schools. Data were collected through the administration of questionnaires on the selected respondents. The collected data was then processed and analysed using descriptive and

inferential statistics with the aid of mean and standard deviation. The study established the following findings: Secondary schools in the study area differed in the number of guidance and counselling services that they offer. Teacher counsellors had little training in guidance and counselling while Stakeholders adequately supported guidance and counselling programme in the schools. Based on these findings, it is recommended that there is need to improve the level of training of teacher counselors in guidance and counseling through further on the job training programme, further schooling for better skill development and competence as this will tell on the offering of all the services required for a focused and positive guidance and counselling programme.

Odhiambo (2014) investigated influence of guidance and counselling programme on academic performance of students in selected public secondary schools in Molo Sub County, Nakuru County, Kenya. The study adopted an ex post facto design and targeted 1385 Form Four students and 24 teacher counsellors in 24 public secondary schools in Molo Sub County. Random sampling was used to select a sample size of 86 students and 12 teacher counselors. Data was collected by the use of questionnaires. Descriptive statistics comprising means and standard deviations were used to analyse the data. Inferential statistics which included Pearson's correlation was used in data analysis. The hypotheses were tested at 0.01 level of significance. Data was analysed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21 for windows. The study concluded that guidance and programmes have a positive impact on the academic performance of students. Based on the study findings, it is recommended that teacher counsellors should implement all the services required for a guidance and programme. Also guidance and programme should be strengthened in order to improve the academic performance of secondary schools in the area.

Bolu-Steve and Oredugba (2017) examined influence of counseling services on perceived academic performance of secondary school students in Lagos State. At the first stage, the researchers purposively selected Ikorodu L.G.A in Lagos State. Six hypotheses were generated for the purpose of the study. Data were gathered using researchers' designed instrument tagged "Influence of Counselling Service on Academic Performance of Students Questionnaire (ICAPSQ)". The findings of this study revealed that there was no significant difference on the basis of age, class level and school type. However a significant difference was found on the basis of respondent's religion, gender and the number of times the students visited the counsellor. It was therefore recommended that the ministry of education should ensure that guidance and counselling units are established in all public and private secondary schools in Nigeria.

Orewere et al. (2020) investigated the effect of guidance and counselling services on students' career choice in selected secondary schools of Jos metropolis. Descriptive research design of the survey type was used. Data were gathered using a researcher designed instrument tagged "Effect of Guidance and Counselling Services on Students' Career Choice Questionnaire (EGCSSCCQ)". Data obtained from the field were presented through the use of frequency tables and simple percentages while the chi-square (X^2) was used to test the formulated hypotheses for the study at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study showed that there was no significant difference on the basis guidance and counselling services offered to students' and on the influence of career choice provided to students. Based on these findings, the researchers recommended that more guidance and counselling center should be set-up with more professional counsellors employed in the schools and also Government should support guidance and counselling practically by providing funds.

Ondima et al. (2013) determined effectiveness of guidance and counselling programme in enhancing students' academic, career and personal competencies: A Case of Secondary Schools in Nyamira District, Kenya. The study utilized ex-post facto causal comparative design. The respondents of the study were 18 head teachers, 18 teacher counsellors and 302 students drawn from a population of 3,752 form three students, 47 head teachers and 47 teacher counsellors. Data for the study were collected using open and close ended questionnaires and interview schedules. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. Means, frequencies and percentages were the descriptive statistics while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was the inferential statistic used. All the respondents who participated in the study perceived school guidance and counselling programme as effective in enhancing students' academic, career and personal competencies. It was recommended that guidance and counselling programme be implemented and fully supported as a matter of priority in all secondary schools to equip all students with necessary academic, career and personal competencies.

Ng'eno and Magut (2014) examined students' perception of the impact of Guidance and Counseling programmes on the Satisfaction of Vocational needs in selected Kenyan secondary schools. The target population for the study was all students drawn from secondary schools in North and South Rift Valley region of Kenya. Four hundred and fifty students were selected through stratified random sampling from ten secondary schools. Self-developed questionnaires were used for data collection. Ex post facto research design was utilized for the study. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to test null hypothesis at .05 level of significance. The findings indicated that the respondents perception on the impact of guidance and counseling on satisfaction of vocational needs was uncertain (neutral perception) which meant that the impact was not significant.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population size of this study comprised of all the teacher counselors in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

The sample of this study comprised of 28 teacher counsellors from public secondary schools in Rivers State. Students of the senior secondary school students were also part of the study because they are the group of persons that benefits directly from guidance and counselling. Also, it is because the guidance and counselling practices by teachers are well known to them, especially as it relates to how it affects their academic performance. Ten (10) students were chosen from each of the fourteen (14) randomly selected schools, therefore, the study dealt with 140 students.

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled: "Guidance and Counselling Questionnaire (GCQ)" and Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (SAPQ). The instruments were divided into two sections. Section 'A' was used to gather the demographic data of the respondents, while section 'B' addressed issues relating to research questions and hypotheses of the study. The responses on section B was patterned after a modified four point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) rated 4, 3, 2, and 1. Also, Yes (2) and No (1) likert scale was involved in addressing the first research question.

The instruments were validated by the researcher's supervisor for observation and content modification. The quality and relevance of the items, including appropriateness, clarity

and sufficiency of the instrument for collecting required responses from the respondents was scrutinized. All inputs such as corrections or comments from the supervisor were built into final draft of the questionnaire. The researcher also cross checked the items with the research questions to ensure that the instruments were adequate for the study.

To determine the reliability of the instrument, the researcher carried out a pilot study that preceded the primary research that was used to ascertain the reliability of the research instruments. This was done by administering thirty (30) copies of the questionnaire instruments to teacher counsellors and students of the selected public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria who were not part of the sample but were part of the population. The copies were retrieved and correlated using Cronbach Alpha Correlation Coefficient. As such a reliability index of .832 was realised. Frequencies, charts and simple percentages were used to analyse the demographic data of the respondents. Mean and standard deviation analysis were used in answering the research questions, while ANOVA associated with simple regression was employed in testing the hypothesis formulated for the study at .05 level of significance. This was done using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

RESULTS

Demographic Data of Respondents

This section looks at the demography of the participants, which helped in explaining the distribution of respondents. The guidance and counsellors were in the public secondary schools in Rivers State were distributed according to their location, gender, working experience and educational qualification.

Figure 1: Distribution of Questionnaire to Participants

The pie chart in figure 1, revealed that 16(57%) of the teacher counsellors were from urban schools, while 12(43%) of them were from rural public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Figure 2: Percentage distribution of respondents on gender

The pie chart in Figure 2, revealed that 11(39%) of the respondents were male, while 17(61%) of the respondents were females.

Figure 3: Percentage distribution of respondents on working experience

The bar chart in Figure 3, revealed that 3(11%) of the respondents have worked as teacher counselors between 1-5 years, 14(50%) of them have worked between 6-10 years, 6(21%) of them have between 10-15 years working experience, while 5(18%) of the respondents were have above 15 years working experience.

Figure 4: Percentage distribution of respondents on educational qualification

The bar chart in Figure 4, showed that 4(14%) of the respondents have OND/HND as their highest educational qualification, 11(39%) of them have BSc/B.Ed., 10(36%) of them have M.Sc/M.Ed., while 3(11%) of the respondents have other degree as their highest educational qualification.

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question One: What are the various types of guidance and counselling services present in secondary schools in in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Figure 5: Percentage response on types of guidance and counselling services

The bar chart in Figure 1 revealed that 19(68%) said they have information counselling services in their school, 9(32%) said they don't have. 20(71%) said they have orientation counselling, while 8(29%) said they don't. Also, 15(54%) said they have placement counselling, while

13(46%) said they do not. Furthermore, 21(75%) of the respondents said they have appraisal counselling services, while 7(25%) said they don't have such.

Research Question Two: How does information counselling service affect academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of respondents answer to the extent information counselling service affect academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Teacher Counsellors		Students		Weighted Mean	Remark
		Mean	SD.	Mean	SD.		
1	This counselling service helps to develop and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students	3.18	0.86	3.39	0.83	3.29	Agree
2	Information counselling helps students make adequate preparation for their exams	3.11	0.96	3.29	0.81	3.20	Agree
3	This counselling service make students avoid behaviour that can mar good academic performance	3.07	0.77	3.25	0.65	3.16	Agree
4	Information counselling service helps students identify various tips that can guide them as students	3.18	0.67	3.32	0.67	3.25	Agree
5	Information counselling service helps students use various study method techniques learnt during group counselling	3.11	0.79	3.14	0.80	3.13	Agree
Grand mean		3.13	0.81	3.28	0.75	3.21	Agree

Data on Table 1 shows that all the items had weighted mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were perceived as the extent information counselling service affect academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. In summary, with an aggregate weighted mean of 3.21 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, the respondents agreed to a high extent that information counselling service helps to develop and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students, information counselling helps students make adequate preparation for their exams, information counselling service make students avoid behaviour that can mar good academic performance, information counselling service helps students identify various tips that can guide them as students and information counselling service helps students use various study method techniques learnt during group counselling. This finding have demonstrated the importance of information counselling services in secondary schools, especially as it affects students' academic performance positively.

Test of Hypothesis

HO₁: Information counselling service does not significantly affect academic performance of secondary school students Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of One Way ANOVA Analysis on the effect of Information counselling service on academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria

	Sum of Squares	Df.	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	342.836	3	114.279	9.519	.000
Within Groups	288.129	24	12.005		
Total	630.964	27			

Table 3 revealed the analysis of variance on the effect of Information counselling service on academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria, which yielded a mean square of 114.279 (between groups) and 12.005 (within groups). This produced an F-value of 9.519 which has a sig value at .000 (2-tailed). Since the significance value is less than .05 alpha value used for the test, a significant effect exists. The researcher rejected the null hypothesis, and concluded that information counselling service significantly affect academic performance of secondary school students Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Types of Guidance and Counselling Services Present in Secondary Schools

The study revealed that 19(68%) have information counselling services in their school, 20(71%) have orientation counselling, Also, 15(54%) have placement counselling. Furthermore, 21(75%) of the respondents said they have appraisal counselling services. This implies that information, orientation, placement and appraisal counselling services were seen to be present in most public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. All these services aimed at improving the academic standard of secondary school students. Counselling services has a lot of impact on students' academic performance. Engaging in placement counselling, in schools will help in placing students in an appropriate class or school, courses, training or vocations. In this case, the counsellors assist the students to select the right subject combination in line with their identified traits.

This practice is useful in carrying out the placement of these students, especially in selecting subject areas. This is needed because; most of the secondary school students does not really know how to make choice based on their likes. This aspect of counselling programme of course will help them know what the particular discipline to pursue in higher institution. When orientation counselling programme are employed in schools, it will help the new students to be acquainted with the academic environment, since the school is usually new to the students. An orientation activity aids the students to regulate to the new environment. At this point, students are directed to the rules and regulation guiding behavior and interpersonal relationship within the school. In information counselling practice, the school guidance counsellor provides the students with accurate information on educational, vocational and personal social opportunities facts that are available in order to assist the students in making informed decision and choices.

Modo et al. (2013) noted that students who are exposed to educational guidance and counselling services perform in their study better than their counterparts. This could be attributed to orientation given to them, during their admission. Appraisal counselling services was identified to be more practiced as compared to other counselling services in the present study. Orewere, Ogenyi and Dogun (2020) investigated the effect of guidance and counselling services on students' career choice in selected secondary schools of Jos metropolis. The findings of this

study showed that there was no significant difference on the basis guidance and counselling services offered to students' and on the influence of career choice provided to students. This shows that the students embraced all the counselling methods they were exposed to. Also, it could be that the teacher counsellors employed the same strategy during their counselling sessions. This implies that all the guidance and counselling services were all considered important. This agrees with findings of the present study. This important outcome underscores the significance of guidance and counseling in the schools, which is their duty to enlighten the students about requirements and condition of success, advantages and disadvantages, opportunities and prospects in the different lines of work.

Effect of Information Counselling Service on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students

From the study, the respondents agreed to a high extent that information counselling service helps to develop and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students, information counselling helps students make adequate preparation for their exams, information counselling service make students avoid behaviour that can mar good academic performance, information counselling service helps students identify various tips that can guide them as students and information counselling service helps students use various study method techniques learnt during group counselling. Also, it was revealed that students perform better when they are exposed to counselling and students' performance improves when they follow various tips by counsellors. Furthermore, information counselling service significantly affects academic performance of secondary school students Rivers State, Nigeria. These assertions were supported by Carey and Harrington (2010) as they noted that counselling services assist students at all levels to become fully acquainted with occupational and educational opportunities that is at their disposal, as well as helps to develop and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students, which will encourage decent behaviour. Adeoye (2016) validated the outcome of the present study by, stressing how counsellors are needed in guiding students during transition from junior to senior class level in the secondary school.

Eremie and Bethel-Eke (2020) investigated influence of guidance and counselling services on career choice and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. It was found that there is no significant difference in the opinion of students on the extent to which educational, vocational and personal social counselling services influence career choice and academic achievement of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. This assertion agrees with the present study only that, no specific counselling service was mentioned. In a similar study, Eremie and Jackson (2019) examined the Influence of Guidance and Counseling Services on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Rivers State. The findings revealed that Information services significantly influence academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. This validates the relevance of information services in secondary schools.

Furthermore, Okita (2012) examined the influence of guidance and programme on academic performance of students in secondary schools in Molo Sub County, Nakuru County, Kenya. It was revealed that guidance and programmes have a positive impact on the academic performance of students. This implies that when teacher counsellors implement all the services required for a guidance and programme, students' academic performance will be improved.

CONCLUSION

Considering the findings obtained in this study it is concluded that there is no guidance and counselling services that are not of importance in secondary school education. The emphasis placed on guidance and counseling in the schools is such that teachers see it as their duty to enlighten the students about requirements and condition of success, advantages and disadvantages, opportunities and prospects in the different fields of endeavor. It was noted that counselling practices assist students at various forms at becoming fully acquainted with various occupational and educational opportunities that is at their disposal, as well as helps to advance and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students, which will encourage decent behaviour. When teachers counsellors implements all the guidance and counselling services needed, students' academic outcome will be improved. Moreover, Teacher counsellors had small training in guidance and counselling while educational stakeholders adequately supported guidance and counselling programme in public schools. When various secondary schools employ counselling service that benefits them most with the involvement of educational stakeholders, it will promotes the practice of guidance and counselling in schools. Furthermore, due to teacher's being engaged in heavy workload, which makes them have busy schedule, many students regards and perceive the teacher counsellor as a teacher first then a counsellor.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that:

- Teacher counsellors should be made to attend professional conferences to learn new ideas of therapies with clients. This is important because, counselling helps to improve students' academic performance, as well as make them understand what they really want in life.
- Government should encourage guidance and counselling practically in secondary schools by providing and making funds available for all the services in guidance and counselling. This is because, it helps to advance and maintain good interpersonal relationship among students and staff.

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